

OCEAN:ICE News – December 2024

OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN:ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Season's Greetings and Welcome to December's Edition of OCEAN:ICE News!

As 2024 draws to a close, we extend congratulations to the entire OCEAN:ICE community for yet another productive year. Together, we've made progress in advancing our understanding of ocean-ice interactions, achieving key milestones, and furthering the ambitious goals of this Horizon Europe project.

In this issue, we're pleased to bring you the latest updates. Meet our featured researcher of the month and learn about recent activities, including CHINARE, the SOOS WSDML Workshop, and the NCKF Climate Research Symposium. We're also excited to highlight the deployment of an Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV) in the Amundsen Sea during the RVIB Araon / KOPRI Cruise 2023/2024, a significant step forward in understanding the complex processes affecting the coastal components of the West Antarctic Ice Sheet. Don't forget to check out highlights from our Climate Coffees and mark your calendars for upcoming events.

As we look ahead to 2025, we remain inspired by OCEAN:ICE dedication and expertise. With new challenges and opportunities on the horizon, we're confident in our continued success in uncovering critical insights into our planet's climate system.

In the spirit of the holiday season, we send warm wishes for a joyful and rejuvenating break. Here's to a successful 2025 filled with groundbreaking discoveries, strengthened collaborations, and impactful contributions to science and society.

We hope you enjoy this month's updates and look forward to sharing more in the new year!

Happy Holidays and a Happy New Year!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Rachael Sanders

Check out our latest 'Researcher in the Spotlight' feature on Rachael Sanders, an oceanography Postdoc at [British Antarctic Survey](#).

Read the feature on Rachael [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN:ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN:ICE Activities

OCEAN:ICE at the Chinese Arctic and Antarctic Administration (CHINARE)

OCEAN:ICE took part in the Chinese Arctic and Antarctic Administration (CHINARE) in Shanghai on 29 October to 1 November. WP1 co-lead [Pierre Dutrieux \(BAS\)](#) was invited to present his work in the polar physical processes session and used the opportunity to highlight the OCEAN:ICE project.

The 40th Anniversary of CHINARE was to foster collaboration and research in polar science. The symposium also outlined the progress and development plans of the Fifth International Polar Year (IPY5).

You can read the full article [here](#).

CHINARE 2024

OCEAN:ICE at the SOOS Weddell Sea and Dronning Maud Land Workshop

The OCEAN:ICE attended the annual virtual meeting for the Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS) Weddell Sea and Dronning Maud Land (WSDML) regional working group workshop. This workshop, chaired by OCEAN:ICE's very own [Markus Janout \(AWI\)](#), brought together regional researchers from around the globe.

[Andrew Meijers \(BAS\)](#) gave an overview of the ongoing and upcoming OCEAN:ICE science in the region, focusing on the upcoming mooring retrievals in WP5, float deployments in WP1, ice shelf cavity research and datasets in WP2, and the coordinated modeling activities across WP1, WP4, WP5, and WP6.

Read more on the [website](#).

OCEAN:ICE at NCKF Climate Research Symposium

On the 28th of October, the OCEAN:ICE project coordinator, [Ruth Mottram \(DMI\)](#), has delivered the keynote at the NCKF Climate Research Symposium 2024 on 'Sea level rise from Antarctica: Have we already passed the tipping point?'

The National Center for Climate Research (NCKF) at the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI) hosts the symposium which gathers climate scientists and non-science stakeholders.

Read the full article [here](#).

Deployment of AUV in the Amundsen Sea on RVIB Araon / KOPRI Cruise 2023/2024

An international expedition, led by Chief Scientist Won Sang Lee from KOPRI, and hosting participants from Korea, Sweden, UK, US, Australia and China, took place aboard the Korean icebreaker RVIB Araon between December 28, 2023, to February 15, 2024. The focus of the expedition was Thwaites Glacier and the two adjacent ice shelves in the Amundsen Sea, Dotson ice shelf and Getz ice shelf.

The expedition marked significant progress in understanding the complex processes affecting the coastal components of the West Antarctic Ice Sheet. The data collected offer critical inputs for refining predictions of glacier behaviour and future sea level rise and will be used in years to come in studies of the West Antarctic Ice Sheet and its impact on climate, sea level, and the marine coastal system around Antarctica.

Read the full article [here](#).

Photo: cruise participants

OCEAN:ICE Deliverables Submitted

The OCEAN:ICE community has been busy recently submitting various deliverables:

- D7.4 '[Infrastructure design v.1.0'](#)
- D7.7 '[Interoperability requirements definition'](#)
- D7.9 '[Web Data Portal v1.0'](#)
- D7.11 '[System performance, monitoring and impact assessment r.1.0'](#)
- D10.1 '[Report on development and delivery of training on Argo floats for the National Antarctic Scientific Center'](#)

The progress and results of OCEAN:ICE are published in deliverables and milestone reports.

In order to keep up with the OCEAN:ICE deliverables and milestones, visit our [website](#) and stay tuned on our social media channels.

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Happening Soon

OCEAN:ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 27-30 January 2025, [Arctic Frontiers 2025: Beyond Borders](#), Tromsø, Norway
- 20-28 March 2025, [Arctic Science Summit Week / ICARP IV Summit](#), Boulder, Colorado, USA

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN:ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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Who is OCEAN:ICE?

OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN:ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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